

The role of cardiology and dietetics in the complex therapy of glaucoma: effects on intraocular pressure, neuroprotection, and cardiovascular support

El papel de la cardiología y la dietética en la terapia compleja del glaucoma: efectos sobre la presión intraocular, neuroprotección y soporte cardiovascular

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Abstract

Cardiovascular factors play a key role in the pathogenesis and progression of glaucoma, affecting intraocular pressure and blood supply to the optic nerve. Arterial hypertension, hypotension, atherosclerosis, as well as microcirculation disorders can exacerbate ischemic damage to the optic nerve and contribute to deterioration of the functional state of the ocular structures. These cardiovascular pathologies require special attention when choosing a treatment strategy for glaucoma patients.

One of the key areas of complex therapy is cardiological monitoring and correction of cardiovascular diseases, which minimizes systemic risks and improves blood supply to the visual organs. Along with this, rational nutrition plays an important role in reducing intraocular pressure, maintaining vascular tone and neuroprotection. This paper considers an interdisciplinary approach combining

cardiological support and dietary recommendations for glaucoma patients. Special attention is paid to vascular risk management, reduction of intraocular pressure, prevention of hypoxic complications and slowing of neurodegenerative processes. Data on the role of systemic factors in the progression of the disease and the importance of their control in order to maximize the effectiveness of therapy are presented.

This integrative approach allows not only to slow down the progression of glaucoma, but also to improve the patient's overall health, creating conditions for maintaining the quality of life and preserving visual functions.

Keywords: cardiology, cardiovascular factors, glaucoma, intraocular pressure, dietetics, neuroprotection, antioxidants, omega-3 fatty acids, nutrition, oxidative stress, metabolic disorders, microcirculation, nutritional support.

Los factores cardiovasculares desempeñan un papel clave en la patogénesis y progresión del glaucoma, afectando la presión intraocular y el suministro de sangre al nervio óptico. La hipertensión arterial, la hipotensión, la aterosclerosis y los trastornos de la microcirculación pueden exacerbar el daño isquémico del nervio óptico y contribuir al deterioro del estado funcional de las estructuras oculares. Estas patologías cardiovasculares requieren una atención especial a la hora de elegir una estrategia de tratamiento para los pacientes con glaucoma.

Una de las áreas clave de la terapia compleja es la monitorización cardiológica y la corrección de enfermedades cardiovasculares, que minimiza los riesgos sistémicos y mejora el suministro de sangre a los órganos visuales. Junto a esto, la nutrición racional juega un papel importante en la reducción de la presión intraocular, el mantenimiento del tono vascular y la neuroprotección. Este artículo considera un enfoque interdisciplinario que combina apoyo cardiológico y recomendaciones dietéticas para pacientes con glaucoma. Se presta especial atención a la gestión del riesgo vascular, la reducción de la presión intraocular, la prevención de complicaciones hipóxicas y la desaceleración de los procesos neurodegenerativos. Se presentan datos sobre el papel de los factores sistémicos en la progresión de la enfermedad y la importancia de su control para maximizar la eficacia de la terapia.

Este enfoque integrador permite no sólo frenar la progresión del glaucoma, sino también mejorar la salud general del paciente, creando las condiciones para mantener la calidad de vida y preservar las funciones visuales.

Palabras clave: cardiología, factores cardiovasculares, glaucoma, presión intraocular, dietética, neuroprotección, antioxidantes, ácidos grasos omega-3, nutrición, estrés oxidativo, trastornos metabólicos, microcirculación, soporte nutricional.

Glaucoma is a progressive optical neuropathy, which results in the excavation of the optic disc and apoptosis of retinal ganglion cells¹. This disease, according to statistics, affects 3.5% of people aged 40 to 80 years and is the main cause of irreversible blindness in the world². Common risk factors for glaucoma are old age, a positive family history, and increased intraocular pressure (IOP). After diagnosis of glaucoma, most patients require lifelong treatment. Timely diagnosis can slow down the progression of the disease, but diagnosis is often complicated because visual field loss can be asymptomatic until late stages.

In recent years, researchers have increasingly focused on systemic factors affecting the course of glaucoma, such as cardiovascular diseases and metabolic disorders. The state of the cardiovascular system has a significant impact on the pathogenesis of glaucoma. Hypertension, hypotension, atherosclerosis, and other vascular disorders can worsen ischemic damage to the optic nerve and impair its blood supply. These conditions are often observed in patients with glaucoma, which requires an integrated approach to treatment with the participation of a cardiologist.

In recent years, with the deepening understanding of the pathological mechanism of glaucoma, researchers have begun to pay more and more attention to the role of dietary factors in the pathogenesis of glaucoma. Nutrients, antioxidants, vitamins, organic compounds and trace elements are positioned by experts as integrative strategic components independent of IOP for delaying or stopping glaucomatous degeneration of retinal ganglion cells.

Accordingly, it is extremely important to consider the latest approaches and technologies in the diagnosis and treatment of glaucoma, taking into account diet therapy, as well as to determine their impact on the management of intraocular pressure.

During the preparation of this study, a systematic review of publications on the topic of the work was conducted, including meta-analyses and review articles, which allowed us to summarize knowledge about diagnostic methods and therapeutic approaches. The recommendations and clinical protocols published by national and international ophthalmological associations were also studied. In addition, various diagnostic and therapeutic methods, including traditional and modern approaches, were compared, which revealed their advantages and disadvantages. Of particular interest was the study of specific cases of glaucoma patients in order to assess the role of diet therapy in correcting this pathology.

Through the application of a systematic approach, glaucoma has been considered as a complex system interacting with various factors such as genetics, environment, and behavioral aspects, including the nutritional characteristics of patients. An analysis of the interrelationships between these factors and their impact on the development and course of the disease and its therapy was also carried out.

During the preparation of the work, artificial intelligence and machine learning methods were used to analyze patient data and predict treatment outcomes. The experience of glaucoma patients, including their perception of the disease, treatment approaches and interactions with medical professionals, was studied, and surveys and interviews were conducted to obtain high-quality information about the needs and expectations of patients.

Glaucoma, as one of the leading causes of vision loss worldwide, is estimated to affect 76 million people aged 40-80 years and is expected to increase to 112 million by 2040. The disease threatens and damages the optic nerve and its visual pathways, eventually leading to permanent vision loss, seriously affecting the quality of life. Clinically, glaucoma is divided into three main categories: primary, secondary and congenital. In addition, open-angle glaucoma (OAG) and angle-closure glaucoma (ACG) are distinguished³.

The most common type of glaucoma, primary glaucoma, affects 74% of patients. Several types of secondary OAG are much less common. Pigmented glaucoma occurs when friction between the areas of the lens and the pigment epithelium of the iris releases pigment granules that increase the resistance to outflow. Exfoliative glaucoma, the most common form of secondary glaucoma, occurs when microscopic clusters of protein fibers are synthesized inside the eye and clog the trabecular membrane.

Angle-closure glaucoma is a rapidly progressive ocular neuropathy characterized by occlusion of at least 270° of the iridocorneal angle. Angle-closure glaucoma is only three times less common than OAG, but it causes about 50% of all cases of blindness caused by glaucoma. Primary ACG, which occurs due to pupillary block, has a global prevalence of 0.6%. There are several secondary types of ACG. Neovascular glaucoma, new blood vessels that clog a corner, can develop due to occlusion of the central retinal vein or diabetic retinopathy and usually has a poor prognosis for vision. Phacomorphic glaucoma involves closure of an angle due to swelling of the lens (progressive cataract), and removal of the cataract usually results in restoration of vision.

The state of the cardiovascular system plays an important role in the pathogenesis of glaucoma, affecting both the blood supply to the optic nerve and the regulation of intraocular pressure (IOP). Arterial hypertension, arterial hypotension, atherosclerosis and other vascular disorders not only increase the risk of developing glaucoma but also accelerate the progression of the disease. These conditions lead to chronic ischemia of the optic nerve, impaired autoregulation of blood flow in the peripapillary structures, and increased vulnerability of retinal ganglion cells to damage.

Hypertension, one of the most common cardiovascular pathologies, can maintain adequate blood supply to the optic nerve in the early stages due to high systemic pressure. However, chronic hypertension causes structural changes in the vascular wall, including sclerosis and decreased elasticity of the arteries, which reduces the

vessels' ability to adapt to changes in intraocular pressure. In addition, prolonged hypertension may increase the risk of developing glaucoma optic neuropathy.

On the other hand, arterial hypotension poses an even greater risk for patients with glaucoma, as insufficient systemic blood pressure leads to deterioration of optic nerve perfusion. Nocturnal hypotension, which is observed in patients with circadian rhythm disorders, is especially dangerous. This condition can contribute to the development of glaucoma lesions even with normal levels of intraocular pressure.

Atherosclerosis, characterized by plaque formation and loss of vascular elasticity, also plays a key role in disrupting the blood supply to the optic nerve. It restricts blood flow, which increases hypoxic and ischemic processes in the eye tissues, making them more susceptible to damage.

In addition, vascular endothelial dysfunction, common to many cardiovascular diseases, is accompanied by dysregulation of vascular tone, platelet aggregation and activation of inflammatory processes, which further aggravates the condition of the optic nerve.

Given the close relationship between glaucoma and cardiovascular diseases, an integrated approach to therapy should include not only the control of intraocular pressure, but also the correction of cardiovascular disorders. In this context, the participation of a cardiologist is necessary to assess the patient's general condition, monitor blood pressure, treat concomitant diseases, and optimize systemic hemodynamics. This interdisciplinary approach allows not only to slow the progression of glau-

coma, but also to improve the quality of life of patients, reducing the risk of systemic complications.

Intraocular pressure (IOP) is the main modifying factor currently being clinically considered in the treatment of glaucoma to prevent progression. IOP is the most important risk factor for the development and worsening of this disease. The diagnosis of glaucoma is usually based on IOP in the presence of thinning of the optic nerve fiber layer, glaucomatous excavation of the optic nerve and loss of the visual field. However, Anderson D. R., Heijl A and their co-authors suggested that mechanisms independent of IOP also play a role: about 30% of patients diagnosed with glaucoma do not have elevated IOP, which suggests that neurodegeneration is the main cause of the disease. In addition, 30-40% of patients have a continuing deterioration of the visual field, despite a decrease in IOP⁴.

Increasingly, experts have expressed the opinion that environmental factors significantly influence the progression of glaucoma. Thus, the researchers note that lifestyle, occupational exposures, geographical differences, socio-economic differences, and climatic conditions play a crucial role in influencing the risk of developing glaucoma, its severity, and progression. Smoking, alcohol consumption, diet, physical activity levels, and exposure to air pollution are associated with the onset and progression of glaucoma through mechanisms such as oxidative stress, inflammation, and neurodegeneration. Taking into account the above, experts propose approaches to reduce the negative impact of the above aspects and develop certain recommendations in this regard.

Table 1. Factors that directly or indirectly influence the development and progression of glaucoma

The influence factor	Mechanism of influence	Researchers who support the priority of this factor
Smoking and alcohol abuse	Smoking causes vasoconstriction and impaired blood supply to the eye tissues, which can increase IOP, one of the key risk factors for glaucoma. Tobacco smoke contains free radicals that damage the cells of the optic nerve and disrupt their functioning. Chronic nicotine exposure impairs microcirculation in the vessels feeding the optic nerve, which exacerbates damage in glaucoma. Regular alcohol abuse leads to toxic effects on nerve tissues, including the optic nerve. Alcohol causes dehydration, which disrupts the fluid balance in the eyes and can contribute to changes in IOP. Chronic alcoholism leads to vascular damage, impairing blood flow and oxygenation of the optic nerve, which contributes to its degeneration.	Rivera JL, Bell NP, Feldman RM ⁵ Kumar A, Ou Y. ⁶ Leske MC. ⁷ Perez CI, Singh K, Lin S. ⁸
Emotional stress	Emotional stress can activate the sympathetic nervous system, which leads to the release of adrenaline and an increase in blood pressure, which in turn can cause an increase in IOP, especially in people prone to glaucoma. Stress causes vasospasm, which impairs the blood supply to the optic nerve. Lack of oxygen and nutrients can increase degenerative changes in the tissues of the eye. Chronic stress is accompanied by increased release of cortisol and increased levels of free radicals, which increases oxidative stress in the body. This condition is associated with cell damage, including cells of the optic nerve, which makes it more vulnerable to destruction in glaucoma.	Ramdas WD, Wolfs RC, Hofman A, de Jong PT, Vingerling JR, Jansonius NM. ⁹
Air pollution	Toxic components of polluted air, such as fine particles (PM2.5), nitrogen and sulfur oxides, increase the level of inflammatory processes in the body, which contributes to damage to the cells of the optic nerve and retina, which can accelerate the progression of glaucoma. Inhaling polluted air impairs the functions of the cardiovascular system. Microcirculation disorders and decreased tissue oxygen saturation negatively affect the blood supply to the optic nerve, increasing the risk of its degeneration in glaucoma. Prolonged exposure to polluted air may be associated with increased intraocular pressure (IOP), the main risk factor for glaucoma.	Hecht I, Achiron A, Man V, Burgansky-Eliash Z. ¹⁰ Blumberg D, Skaat A, Liebmann JM. ¹¹ Gillmann K, Weinreb RN, Mansouri K. ¹²
Improper nutrition	The lack of vitamins A, C, E and other antioxidants in the diet increases oxidative stress in the body, which can damage the cells of the optic nerve. A diet high in sugar and saturated fat contributes to the development of obesity and metabolic disorders such as insulin resistance and diabetes mellitus. These conditions increase the risk of glaucoma by worsening blood flow and increasing IOP. Deficiency of omega-3 fatty acids can contribute to degenerative processes in the visual system. Consuming large amounts of salt increases blood pressure, which negatively affects the vascular system of the eye and can lead to a deterioration in the blood supply to the optic nerve and contribute to the progression of glaucoma. The lack of fiber in the diet slows down the metabolism, which can affect the pressure inside the eye. Water deficiency causes dehydration of tissues, including ocular ones, which disrupts the outflow of intraocular fluid.	Dziedziak J, Kasarello K, Cudnoch-Jędrzejewska A. ¹³ Yang X, Yang Z, Liu Y ¹⁴ Owaifeer AM, Taisan AA. ¹⁵ Leske MC, Heijl A, Hyman L, Bengtsson B. ¹⁶ Psihogios A., Madampage C., Faught B.E. ¹⁷ Cassotta M., Forbes-Hernandez T.Y., Calderon Iglesias R., Ruiz R., ElexpuruZabaleta M., Giampieri F., Battino M. ¹⁸ Vaz-Rodrigues R., Mazuecos L., Villar M., Urra J.M., Gortazar C., de la Fuente J. ¹⁹

Discussion

Thus, in general, the authors emphasize the multifaceted influence of various factors (smoking, alcohol, stress, air pollution and malnutrition) on the development and progression of glaucoma, highlighting the mechanisms of their action and supporting the conclusions of scientific research²⁰. Together, these factors contribute to an increase in IOP, a deterioration in the blood supply to the optic nerve, increased oxidative stress, and the development of systemic vascular pathologies. However, it can be noted that the largest number of researchers consider improper nutrition to be the leading factor influencing the progression of the pathology in question, and among all preventive and curative measures aimed at combating the progression of glaucoma, diet therapy is preferred.

Cardiological aspects play an important role in an integrated approach to the treatment of glaucoma, as the cardiovascular system is closely related to the regulation of intraocular pressure (IOP) and blood supply to the optic nerve. Cardiovascular diseases such as hypertension, hypotension, atherosclerosis, and heart failure can worsen the course of glaucoma, which requires the introduction of cardiological approaches to improve treatment outcomes. Maintaining optimal blood pressure levels plays a key role in preventing hypo- and hyperperfusion of the optic nerve.

A chronic increase in blood pressure is associated with damage to the vascular wall, a decrease in its elasticity

and an increase in vascular resistance, which impairs blood supply to the optic nerve. Hypertension treatment helps to reduce the risk of glaucoma progression, but it is important to avoid excessive lowering of blood pressure, especially in elderly patients. Low blood pressure, especially nocturnal hypotension, is associated with impaired blood flow in the optic nerve, which requires careful monitoring and, if necessary, correction with the use of medications or lifestyle changes²¹.

The state of vascular tone and blood flow directly affects the perfusion of the optic nerve. Cardiological approaches include the use of drugs that improve the rheological properties of blood, such as antiplatelet agents, to prevent thrombosis and improve microcirculation. Atherosclerotic changes in the vessels feeding the optic nerve can cause chronic ischemia. Cardiological interventions aimed at lowering cholesterol (statins), changing diet and lifestyle adjustments contribute to improving blood supply to the eye.

Cardiac arrhythmias (for example, bradycardia, tachycardia) and heart failure can worsen systemic blood flow, which affects the condition of the optic nerve. Treatment of cardiac diseases helps to ensure a stable supply of oxygen and nutrients. Systemic drugs used in cardiology, such as calcium channel blockers, can have a positive effect on lowering IOP by relaxing vascular smooth muscles²².

The close cooperation of an ophthalmologist and a cardiologist makes it possible to take into account both local and systemic factors in the treatment of glaucoma. This approach is aimed not only at reducing intraocular pressure, but also at preventing ischemic damage to the optic nerve, which increases the effectiveness of therapy and helps preserve vision.

In addition, in recent years, with the deepening understanding of the pathological mechanism of glaucoma, researchers have begun to pay more and more attention to the role of dietary factors in the pathogenesis of glaucoma. Although the exact cause of glaucoma is not yet fully understood, existing research suggests that certain dietary habits, such as high-salt diets, are associated with the prevalence of glaucoma.

Existing research suggests that a high-salt diet may be indirectly linked to glaucoma by affecting blood pressure and other physiological mechanisms. A high-salt diet can affect intraocular pressure through a number of complex biological mechanisms, and there is evidence to support the possibility that elevated blood pressure may cause increased intraocular pressure²³.

In addition to the fact that a high-salt diet is associated with a risk of developing glaucoma, it can also affect the progression of glaucoma. Increased salt intake leads to an increase in sodium concentration, which leads to stiffness of endothelial cells and a decrease in the release of nitric oxide from vascular endothelial cells. Dysfunction

of endothelial cells can reduce the bioavailability of nitric oxide and increase the production of reactive oxygen species, which leads to impaired hemodynamics of the eye, while reactive oxygen species can cause cellular aging and apoptosis, which ultimately can lead to apoptosis of optic nerve cells, exacerbating damage to the optic nerve and further exacerbating the progression of glaucoma²⁴.

In contrast, the Mediterranean diet, which is considered one of the healthiest diets in the world due to its abundance of vegetables, fruits, whole grains, legumes, nuts, olive oil, and moderate amounts of fish and wine, focuses on whole foods with low sugar and low processing, with an abundance of vegetables and fruits that are Natural antioxidants containing high levels of vitamin C, vitamin E, beta-carotene, and polyphenolic compounds such as flavonoids and anthocyanins. These antioxidants play a role in the body in fighting free radicals and mitigating oxidative stress, which is a key factor in the development of glaucoma because it can worsen damage to retinal ganglion cells and affect the function of the optic nerve. Thus, the richness of antioxidants in the Mediterranean diet can help protect the optic nerve from oxidative damage and thus play a positive role in slowing down the glaucoma process.

Of particular interest is another diet, Intervention for Neurodegenerative Delay (MIND), which is positioned as a strategy to promote healthy cognitive aging²⁵. It is a combination of the Mediterranean diet and the Dietary approach to hypertension (DASH) diet²⁶ and is associated with a reduction in the incidence of Alzheimer's disease. The main categories of products and recommendations for their consumption are given in Table 2.

Table 2. The main categories of products and recommendations for their consumption as part of the MIND diet

Product Category	Recommendations for	Health benefits	Limitations
Leafy green vegetables	Daily consumption, at least 6 servings per week (spinach, cabbage, lettuce).	They contain vitamin K, lutein, folic acid and beta-carotene, which protect the brain and support cognitive functions.	Improper cooking (frying) can reduce their benefits.
Other vegetables	At least 1 serving per day.	They are rich in fiber, vitamins and minerals, which contributes to the overall health of the body and reduces inflammation.	Limit potatoes in the form of fries or with the addition of butter.
Nuts	About 5 servings per week (almonds, walnuts, hazelnuts).	They provide the body with polyunsaturated fats and antioxidants, improve vascular and brain health.	Avoid salted or sugary nuts.
Berries	At least 2 servings per week (blueberries, strawberries).	High content of antioxidants (especially flavonoids), which protect brain cells from oxidative stress.	Do not use in the form of sweet desserts (jams, syrups).
Legumes	At least 3 servings per week (lentils, beans, chickpeas).	They are rich in vegetable protein, fiber and B vitamins, which promote vascular health and lower cholesterol levels.	Avoid canned legumes with a high salt content.
Whole grain products	At least 3 servings per day (oatmeal, whole grain bread, brown rice).	They improve metabolism, help maintain stable blood sugar levels and reduce the risk of neurodegeneration.	Exclude products made from white flour.
Fish	At least once a week (salmon, mackerel, herring).	Omega-3 fatty acids support brain health, reduce inflammation, and improve vascular function.	Exclude fried fish and foods with added oil.
Bird	At least 2 servings per week.	It is a good source of low-fat protein that supports brain tissue and overall health.	Reduce consumption on the skin and in fried form.
Olive oil	The main oil for cooking.	It contains monounsaturated fats and antioxidants that reduce the risk of inflammation and support vascular health.	Avoid overheating, which destroys useful substances.
Limited Products	Red meat, butter, cheese, sweets, fried dishes, fast food.	Limiting saturated fats and sugars reduces inflammation, improves vascular function, and slows down the aging process of the brain.	Severely limit the frequency of consumption and portions.

The developed diet offers a scientifically based, comprehensive approach to nutrition that supports the health of the brain, eyes and the entire body. She focuses on beneficial nutrients and their mechanisms of action, while excluding potentially harmful products. Experts point out that the eyes and brain share a common embryonic origin, since the retina and optic nerve branch off from the midbrain during embryonic development. Thus, despite their diverse morphology, retinal ganglion cells exhibit typical properties of central nervous system neurons. In addition, for example, open-angle glaucoma (OAG) and Alzheimer's disease have many common biochemical and pathological changes. Accordingly, according to the authors of the MIND diet, it has a neuroprotective effect not only on the brain, but also on the eyes.

Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids play a significant role in preventing and slowing the progression of glaucoma. They are a group of essential nutrients that include alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), stearic acid (SA), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA), docosapentaenoic acid (DPA), and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA).

A cross-sectional study using data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) database (2005-2008) with 3,865 participants aged 40 years and older showed that increasing the proportion of omega-3 fatty acids in the daily diet may have a protective effect against glaucoma²⁷. In recent years, research has shown that a higher intake of omega-3 fatty acids may have the potential to reduce the risk of glaucoma and that omega-3 fatty acids may have a protective effect on glaucoma through various mechanisms such as lowering intraocular pressure, regulating blood supply, relieving inflammation, and reducing oxidative stress. In a study on rats, experts were able to identify that omega-3 fatty acids can reduce intraocular pressure by increasing the outflow of aqueous humor from the atria²⁸. In addition, oral intake of omega-3 fatty acids has been shown to significantly improve IOP and omega-3 has been found to have a neuroprotective effect on the retina in a mouse model of hereditary glaucoma²⁹.

Vitamins, as key dietary supplements, have been extensively studied in recent years in studies examining their

effect on the common disease glaucoma. Several studies have attempted to identify a potential association of vitamins A, E, C, B, K1, and D with the incidence and severity of glaucoma³⁰.

The researchers investigated the relationship between vitamin B and glaucoma and found that increased vitamin B6 intake is negatively associated with glaucoma risk, providing new evidence for the potential role of vitamin B6 in glaucoma prevention. In addition, another animal study revealed the positive effect of vitamin B3 (niacin) on glaucoma and other age-related neurodegenerative diseases, which highlights its potential value in neuroprotection³¹.

Vitamin A (retinol) is a fat-soluble nutrient. It has been proven to have neuroprotective ability³². This function is associated with a fully transformable form of retinol, which has been shown in experimental studies conducted on rats. Vitamin A is an ancient remedy for food blindness, including xerophthalmia, keratomalacia, and ocular manifestations of hypovitaminosis A. Dietary supplements and fortification are recommended to slow the widespread spread of vitamin A deficiency. Studies have shown that vitamin A may be useful for the treatment of degenerative diseases of the retina, such as age-related macular degeneration and Stargardt's disease³³.

Vitamin B1, also known as thiamine, is a water-soluble vitamin consisting of two heterocyclic rings, which include a ring of thiazol and pyrimidine connected by a methylene group. Thiamine is relatively stable in acidic solutions, but reacts to heat, oxygen, and light. Biologically, thiamine is an important coenzyme for completing processes such as the conversion of pyruvate to acetyl-CoA in the citric acid cycle to produce ATP, carbon dioxide, and other reducing agents. As a coenzyme in this process, thiamine is present in its active form, thiamine pyrophosphate (TPP). One study found a link between thiamine intake and reduced disease progression in glaucoma patients with normal blood pressure³⁴.

Riboflavin plays an important role in cell repair and growth, given that it helps eliminate free radicals that can damage cells and cause chronic diseases. Experts have suggested that riboflavin may have a protective effect against the development and progression of age-related macular degeneration and glaucoma due to its antioxidant properties and active involvement in gene expression and cellular signaling pathways³⁵. Another study revealed the protective effect of vitamin C on the nervous system and suggested that vitamin C may have therapeutic potential in neurodegenerative diseases such as glaucoma³⁶.

Numerous studies have revealed a complex relationship between mineral intake and glaucoma risk. Calcium is an important mineral for maintaining normal intraocular pressure, and calcium channel blockers are commonly used in the treatment of glaucoma. Experts studied the relationship between the use of calcium channel blockers

(CCBs) and the risk of glaucoma at the British biobank and showed that the use of CCBs (but not other antihypertensive drugs) was associated with an increased risk of glaucoma (odds ratio [OR], 1.39 [95% CI, 1.14–1.69]; $p = 0.001$) / In general, adequate intake of minerals is necessary to maintain eye health and prevent glaucoma, but excessive or improper use can be counterproductive.

Nutritional support is an important component of glaucoma prevention and treatment³⁷. Proper nutrition can have an effect on intraocular pressure, the health of the optic nerve and the general condition of the body, which helps slow the progression of the disease. Antioxidants play a key role in protecting cells from oxidative stress, which damages the tissues of the eye, including the optic nerve. Antioxidants include vitamins A, C, E, as well as beta-carotene and selenium. It is recommended to include in the diet foods rich in these vitamins and trace elements, such as broccoli, spinach, carrots, oranges, berries (blueberries, strawberries, cranberries), almonds, walnuts.

Antioxidants help reduce inflammation and oxidative stress by protecting the optic nerve and slowing its degradation. Omega-3 fatty acids found in fish, flaxseed oil, nuts have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects and help improve microcirculation and maintain normal blood supply to the optic nerve, which helps prevent damage to it. They can also help to normalize intraocular pressure, which is important for glaucoma patients. It is recommended to eat fish (salmon, mackerel), flax seeds and nuts (walnuts, almonds).

Excessive salt and sugar intake can increase blood pressure, which has a negative effect on the vascular system and may contribute to the progression of glaucoma. It is recommended to limit salt intake to 5-6 grams per day, as well as reduce the amount of sugar and foods with a high glycemic index. This will help maintain normal blood pressure and improve blood supply to the eye tissues.

Deficiency of B vitamins (especially B12 and folic acid) can worsen the condition of glaucoma patients. B vitamins affect the metabolism of nerve cells and can support the health of the optic nerve. The inclusion of foods rich in B vitamins (brewer's yeast, meat, eggs, green vegetables) in the diet can help maintain the normal state of the nervous tissue.

Zinc and selenium are important antioxidants that help protect cells from damage caused by free radicals. These trace elements can reduce inflammation and maintain the health of the optic nerve. Foods containing zinc (meat, nuts, grains) and selenium (Brazil nuts, seafood) should be part of the diet.

Rational modification of diet, including increasing the intake of antioxidants, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins and trace elements, as well as limiting the intake of salt, sugar and caffeine, can have a positive effect on the prevention and treatment of glaucoma. Proper nutrition sup-

ports eye health, helps control intraocular pressure, and prevents disease progression.

Conclusions. The extensive and multifaceted pathomechanisms of glaucoma, a complex degenerative disease of the optic nerve, require an integrated approach to preventive and therapeutic strategies.

An integrated approach to glaucoma therapy, including the integration of dietary and cardiological methods, significantly increases the effectiveness of treatment and slows down the progression of the disease. The cardiovascular system plays a key role in maintaining blood supply to the optic nerve and regulating intraocular pressure, and systemic pathologies such as hypertension, hypotension, and atherosclerosis have a significant impact on the course of glaucoma.

Cardiological approaches aimed at controlling blood pressure, improving microcirculation and preventing atherosclerotic changes help reduce ischemic damage to the optic nerve and improve overall hemodynamics. The participation of a cardiologist in an interdisciplinary team allows us to take into account the individual characteristics of the patient, optimizing systemic and local health parameters.

A high-salt diet may worsen the progression of glaucoma through mechanisms that affect blood pressure, ocular blood flow, and oxidative stress, indicating the importance of a low-salt diet for glaucoma patients. In contrast, the Mediterranean diet, which is rich in antioxidants, omega-3 fatty acids, and various nutrients beneficial to the optic nerve, may have a protective effect against glaucoma, emphasizing the role of a balanced diet in treating the disease.

Studies on the correlation between the intake of vitamins A, C, E, B-complex, and D, as well as minerals such as calcium, selenium, zinc, and iron, and the risk of glaucoma have yielded different results, but generally indicate the possible benefits of these nutrients in regulating IOP, antioxidant activity, and improving blood flow to the eye. and neuroprotection. Vitamins B6 and B3 (niacin), as well as vitamins C and D in particular, have shown potential preventive value against glaucoma. However, excessive intake of minerals such as calcium and iron may be associated with an increased risk of glaucoma, while selenium intake should be considered with caution. In addition, caffeine consumption and its association with glaucoma risk remind us that even commonly available daily dietary components need to be carefully considered based on individual differences and disease status. Although moderate caffeine consumption does not have a significant effect on the general population, people with a genetic predisposition or a pre-existing predisposition to glaucoma may have an increased IOP and a risk of developing this disease, which suggests that limiting caffeine consumption in this population group should be considered.

Increasing the intake of antioxidants and beneficial fatty acids and limiting excessive intake of potentially harmful minerals and caffeine through rational dietary modification may be important for the prevention and treatment of glaucoma.

References

1. Kang J M et al. Glaucoma Med Clin North Am, 105 (3). 2021.Pp. 493-510
2. ThamYC et al Global glaucoma prevalence and glaucoma burden projections to 2040: a systematic review and meta-analysis Ophthalmology. 2014. 121(11). Pp. 2081 – 2090
3. Stein J. D. et al Adult Glaucoma – screening, diagnosis and treatment: an overview JAMA, 2021. 325.Pp. 164-174
4. Anderson D.R/ (2011) Normal-tension glaucoma (low-tension glaucoma). Indian J Ophthalmol 59(Suppl 1):S97–S101.
5. Dikopf MS, Vajaranant TS, Joslin CE. Systemic disease and long-term intraocular pressure mean, peak, and variability in nonglaucomatous eyes. Am J Ophthalmol 2018; 193: 184–196.
6. Rivera JL, Bell NP, Feldman RM. Risk factors for primary open angle glaucoma progression: what we know and what we need to know. CurrOpinOphthalmol. 2008;19(2):102–106. doi:10.1097/ICU.0b013e3282f493b3
7. Kumar A, Ou Y. From bench to behaviour: the role of lifestyle factors on intraocular pressure, neuroprotection, and disease progression in glaucoma. Clin Experiment Ophthalmol. 2023;51(4):380–394.
8. Leske MC. Factors for glaucoma progression and the effect of treatment: the early manifest glaucoma trial. Arch Ophthalmol. 2003;121(1):48.
9. Perez CI, Singh K, Lin S. Relationship of lifestyle, exercise, and nutrition with glaucoma. CurrOpinOphthalmol. 2019;30(2):82–88.
10. Hecht I, Achiron A, Man V, Burgansky-Eliash Z. Modifiable factors in the management of glaucoma: a systematic review of current evidence. Graefes Arch ClinExpOphthalmol. 2017;255(4):789–796.
11. Blumberg D, Skaat A, Liebmann JM. Emerging risk factors for glaucoma onset and progression [Internet]. Prog Brain Res. 2015; Available from, 81–101.
12. Gillmann K, Weinreb RN, Mansouri K. The effect of daily life activities on intraocular pressure related variations in open-angle glaucoma. Sci Rep. 2021;11(1):6598.
13. Dzedziak J, Kasarek K, Cudnoch-Jędrzejewska A. Dietary antioxidants in age-related macular degeneration and glaucoma. Antioxidants. 2021;10(11):1743.
14. Yang X, Yang Z, Liu Y, et al. The association between long-term exposure to ambient fine particulate matter and glaucoma: a nation-wide epidemiological study among Chinese adults. Int J HygEnvironHealth. 2021;238:113858.
15. Owaifeer A.M, Taisan A.A. The role of diet in glaucoma: a review of the current evidence. OphthalmolTher. 2018;7(1):19–31.
16. Leske MC, Heijl A, Hyman L, Bengtsson B. Early manifest glaucoma trial: design and baseline data. Ophthalmology. 1999;106(11):2144–2153.
17. Psihogios A., Madampage C., Faught B.E. Contemporary nu-

- trition-based interventions to reduce risk of infection among elderly long-term care residents: A scoping review. *PLoS ONE*. 2022;17:e0272513.
18. Cassotta M., Forbes-Hernandez T.Y., Calderon Iglesias R., Ruiz R., ElexpuruZabaleta M., Giampieri F., Battino M. Links between Nutrition, Infectious Diseases, and Microbiota: Emerging Technologies and Opportunities for Human-Focused Research. *Nutrients*. 2020;12:1827.
 19. Vaz-Rodrigues R., Mazuecos L., Villar M., Urrea J.M., Gortazar C., de la Fuente J. Serum biomarkers for nutritional status as predictors in COVID-19 patients before and after vaccination. *J. Funct. Foods*. 2023;101:105412.
 20. Tseng, VL, Topouzis, F, Yu, F, Keskin, C, Pappas, T, Founti, P, et al. Association between dietary salt intake and open angle Glaucoma in the Thessaloniki eye study. *J Glaucoma*. (2022) 31:494–502
 21. Tseng, VL, Topouzis, F, Yu, F, Keskin, C, Pappas, T, Founti, P, et al. Association between dietary salt intake and open angle Glaucoma in the Thessaloniki eye study. *J Glaucoma*. (2022) 31:494–502.
 22. Zhao, D, Cho, J, Kim, MH, and Guallar, E. The association of blood pressure and primary open-angle glaucoma: a meta-analysis. *Am J Ophthalmol*. (2014) 158:615–27.e9
 23. Barany, E. Role of ultra-filtration in the formation of aqueous humor. *Nature*. (1946) 158:665.
 24. Fan Gaskin, JC, Shah, MH, and Chan, EC. Oxidative stress and the role of NADPH oxidase in Glaucoma. *Antioxidants (Basel)*. (2021) 10:238
 25. Ye, H, Liu, Y, Xu, Z, and Wei, X. Fish oil in Glaucoma treatment: from biological functions to clinical potential. *Mol Nutr Food Res*. (2023) 67:e2200727.
 26. Hanyuda, A, Rosner, BA, Wiggs, JL, Negishi, K, Pasquale, LR, and Kang, JH. Long-term alcohol consumption and risk of exfoliation Glaucoma or Glaucoma suspect status among United States health professionals. *Ophthalmology*. (2023) 130:187–97
 27. Wang, YE, Tseng, VL, Yu, F, Caprioli, J, and Coleman, AL. Association of Dietary Fatty Acid Intake with Glaucoma in the United States. *JAMA Ophthalmol*. (2018) 136:141–7.
 28. Nguyen, CT, Bui, BV, Sinclair, AJ, and Vingrys, AJ. Dietary omega 3 fatty acids decrease intraocular pressure with age by increasing aqueous outflow. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*. (2007) 48:756–62
 29. Kalogerou, M, Kolovos, P, Prokopiou, E, Papagregoriou, G, Deltas, C, Malas, S, et al. Omega-3 fatty acids protect retinal neurons in the dba/2j hereditary Glaucoma mouse model. *Exp Eye Res*. (2018) 167:128–39.
 30. Moreno-Montañés, J, Gándara, E, Moreno-Galarraga, L, Hershey, MS, López-Gil, JF, Kales, S, et al. Ace- vitamin index and risk of Glaucoma: the Sun project. *Nutrients*. (2022) 14:5129
 31. Williams, PA, Harder, JM, Foxworth, NE, Cochran, KE, Philip, VM, Porciatti, V, et al. Vitamin B(3) modulates mitochondrial vulnerability and prevents Glaucoma in aged mice. *Science*. (2017) 355:756–60.
 32. Hui F, Tang J, Williams PA, McGuinness MB, Hadoux X, Casson RJ, Coote M, Trounce IA, Martin KR, van Wijngaarden P, Crowston JG. Improvement in inner retinal function in glaucoma with nicotinamide (vitamin B3) supplementation: A crossover randomized clinical trial. *Clin Exp Ophthalmol*. 2020 Sep;48(7):903-914
 33. Perez CI, Singh K, Lin S. Relationship of lifestyle, exercise, and nutrition with glaucoma. *Current opinion in ophthalmology*. 2019;30(2):82-88.
 34. Pasquale, LR, Wiggs, JL, Willett, WC, and Kang, JH. The relationship between caffeine and coffee consumption and exfoliation Glaucoma or Glaucoma suspect: a prospective study in two cohorts. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*. (2012) 53:6427–33.
 35. Kim J.H., Nam W.H., Yoo Y.S. Riboflavin and its role in age-related macular degeneration: A review of current evidence. *Molecules*. 2018;23:2367.
 36. Asani B., Siedlecki J., Wertheimer C., Liegl R., Wolf A., Ohlmann A., Priglinger S., Priglinger C. Anti-angiogenic properties of rapamycin on human retinal pericytes in an in vitro model of neovascular AMD via inhibition of the mTOR pathway. *BMC Ophthalmol*. 2022;22:138
 37. Cavet ME, Vittitow JL, Impagnatiello F, Ongini E, Bastia E. Nitric oxide (NO): an emerging target for the treatment of glaucoma. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*. 2014;55(8):5005-15.